

The Effect of the Long-Term Plan for FabLabs Performance and Sustainability: FabLab ALAHSa Case Study

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Abstract

Reaching a good level of sustainability and increasing performance are challenges facing many FabLabs around the world. The main objective of this research is to measure the effect of the long-term plan on FabLabs performance and sustainability. Researchers discuss the path have been taken by FabLab ALAHSa team to rapidly increase the performance that lead to improve the sustainability indication. Working with operation excellence from planning, doing, checking then adjusting along with flexible but clear goals will help to reach out a high-level performance. FabLab shall identify the gaps in the community, set goals, create programs then set a long-term plan that help to fill the gaps. Result of this research indicate that goals achieved by over 95% in 2020 compare to around 30% for the same period in previous year. In addition, attendance reach over 8200 people while it is less than 1600 before plan set and followed. Researchers recommend that short and long-term plans shall be main part during FabLabs establishment same as 3D printers and electronics. Long-term plan is the guidance for the establishment work and the generator for performance indicators or key performance indicators (KPIs).

Keywords

FabLab ALAHSa, Long-term, Performance, Plan, Sustainability

1 Introduction

FabLabs are spreading in the developing countries since technologies and educated persons become available. (Kohtala, 2017) define FabLab as "shared workshops where citizens can access digital fabrication equipment to design and make their own objects". FabLab is defined by researchers as the place that setup to engage a community to come in to convert their ideas into a reality by providing a digital design, different equipment's and machines, and special engineers who have the knowledge and experience. The services that provided in FabLabs are almost free and most people working in are a volunteer.

Since 2001 with a first FabLab idea was started at the Media Lab in the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), there are almost 2000 Fablabs in more than 149 countries worldwide (FabLab Network, 2021). There are 14 FabLabs in Saudi Arabia where 10 of them were active and 4 were a planned status

(FabLab Network, 2021). These FabLabs were spread in different locations in Saudi Arabia and half of these were located in eastern province where FabLab ALAHSa is located.

FabLab ALAHSa was established in May 2019 which is located in Saudi Arabia at the eastern province in AlAHSa governorate which is 450 km far away from the central region of Saudi Arabia. The total area of FabLab ALAHSa is 600 m² which consist of two floors. The ground floor is 300 m² which divided into electronics and programming zone, 3D printing zone, Computerized Numerical Control (CNC) zone, milling machine zone, laser cutting zone, Fab studio (For media production), brain storming room and Fablab team offices. While the first floor is 300 m² which consist of kids Lab, Arduino and robotics club, two training room, digital club, lounge, game room and cinema. There are 45 different equipment in the FabLab such as electrical and electronics equipments, 3D printing equipments, laser-cutting equipments, CNC and milling machines equipments, media production equipments, and Office equipments. The FabLab is funded by Abdulmonem AlRashed Humanitarian Foundation and it provide different services that include machine booking, Fab studio booking, consultations and conducting workshops and campaigns (Fablab ALAhsa, 2021). FabLab ALAHSa is the first and only digital fabrication Lab in ALAHSa governorate.

There are several challenges that face FabLabs which include the shortage human resources, less of capital resources and inadequate of technical engineers and so on. In order to overcome on these challenges, FabLabs decision makers should have effective solutions such as a clear plan and a clear path to ensure continues operation of FabLabs with a high performance and sustainability.

According to (Terry,1972) "Planning is the selecting and relating of facts and the making and using of assumptions regarding the future in the visualization and formulation of purposed activities believed necessary to achieve desired results". There are several importance of planning such as increasing efficiency, encouraging creativity and innovation, helping to achieve objectives and to motivate the personnel (Samiksha, 2013). There are different types of planning depending on the nature of planning, duration of planning, levels of management and the use of it. In this paper, researchers focus on the duration of planning which can be classified into short-term and long-term. Short term planning is planning which it duration is less than two years while the long-term planning is that duration more than five years. The long-term planning is called also as a strategic planning (Diksah, 2016).

(Fleischmann et al., 2016) in their case study have shown that FabLabs are not naturally conducive to exploring sustainability. In addition, sustainability issues were clearly addressed (in terms of the material used and the conceptual development) and a co-creation process was embraced throughout the study. (Georgiev et al., 2017) proposed a framework for capturing creativity in digital fabrication between human interactions, human tool/machine interactions, and human-design-object interactions that improve the creative performance and experience of all stakeholders in the FabLab and to easily customize the FabLab training to suit any audience. The performance of FabLabs were related with the sustainability as the studies shows. One of the study that concluded that the FabLab that is disconnected from its ecosystem is less productive than one connected to it (Suire, 2016).

The main objective of this research is to measure the effect of the long-term plan for FabLabs performance and sustainability in FabLab ALAHSa as a case study. The importance of this research comes from the need of ensuring the full operation of FabLabs by setting the long –term plan to reach to high performance and sustainability. In addition, this study is conducted to fill the gap of research regarding the impact of setting the long-term plan for FabLabs performance and sustainability. Moreover, this study will guide existing and new FabLabs in how to set a long-term plan that contribute of FabLabs high performance and sustainability.

Figure 1: Wide Angle for Al AHSa Oasis. This Picture have been shared by UNESCO when they include ALAHSa as Largest desert oasis in the world.

Figure 2: Number of handmade products in AlAHSa

2 Understanding your Community

Knowing your customer is an important factor for any business success. The same concept can be used for FabLabs while building plan, start up or expanding. For any kind of FabLab you lead, the way you run the show. Even more, managing the expenses with different kind of fund types either user fund, complementary business, private sponsorship, public sponsorship, grant fund or charity all required to know your client very well (Burn et. al, 2018).

2.1 FabLab AIAHSA Structure and Start up

The Fab Lab located in AIAHSA in east of Saudi Arabia. AIAHSA is biggest oasis in the world and dates is the main agriculture product. In term of manufacturing and trading, AIAHSA was well known in high quality manufacturing product such as clothes, woven, farming and farming tools, swords and knives and wood products with art design (Al-AHSA Newspaper, 2015). Today, AIAHSA is produce oil to the entire world though Ghawar field which is biggest oil field in the world (Al-AHSA Newspaper, 2017).

FabLab AIAHSA is a developing space for art since and technology started in 2018 funded by Abdulmonem AlRashed Humanitarian Foundation as community services program for AlRashed companies (Abdulmonem Al-Rashed Humanitarian Foundation, 2010). This kind of community project could help companies to market themselves and their services in the community. In the other hand, it is count as part of social responsibilities as it is part of the Saudi vision 2030 (National transformation program, 2016).

FabLab AIAHSA current staff are 5 permanent employees and some part time support team as were tabulated in table 1.

Fab Lab member	Roles
Eng. Ahmed Al Hajji	FabLab consultant
Eng. Dawood Al Battat	FabLab Manager
Eng. Mahmood Al Mohammed	FabLab specialist and 3D design
Eng. Reham Al Rashed	FabLab specialist, programming and electronics SME
Batool Mohammed	FabLab specialist and hand craft SME
Fatimah Al Arjan	Social media specialist, scheduler, and public relation for FabLab and the foundation
Ahmed Al Qanbar	Maintenance specialist, mechanical and 3D designer
Rezan Al Sultan	Kids Lab leader and programs developer
Noura Alsady	Kids Lab programs developer

Table 3: The current staff of permanent employees with their roles

2.2 Introduce FabLab to Community

Since AIAHSA is maker community and has experience in manufacturing, introducing FabLab was not difficult but still need some marketing especially for the new generation. One of the program to do that was to schedule school visits with some activities to FabLab facilities. FabLab AIAHSA received huge number of requests to visit and due to that FabLab AIAHSA team decide to have rules and evaluation to make sure we cover the entire region during these schools visits. First, avoid having multiple school visits from same town. Second, select 18 to 26 active student to be part of the visit. Third, always look for new areas especially areas with people have limited resources to elevate them by knowledge and skills. During the year 2019 – 2020 FabLab AIAHSA arrange more than 16 school visit with total number of visitors around 398.

Figure 3: Engineer Nezar during one of the school visits

Figure 4: Engineer Mahmoud during one of the school visits

2.3 Identify the Gap in Community and Draw the Roadmap

Knowing your community is the right path to follow in order to know the need. As much, you know your client you will be able to identify the gap then build the best suitable solution for them, which avoid wasting resources, building organizations and program that not benefit the community, as it should be. In Fablab ALAHSa, we notice that most of people have ideas, but they do not know to build and that they shall use in term of digital fabrication machine, tools and electronics if needed. FabLab ALAHSa team paraphrase the mission based on the gap and road map to be: elevate community from ideas generator to be makers whom at least know how to start the project implementation and main material and equipment needed to be completed.

3 Building up FabLab Long-term Plan

FabLab ALAHSA team headed by Eng. Ahmed Al Hajji started this activity mid 2020 having in mind to list all FabLab activities, looking at community need and try to draw a path that pass through the activities and guide them to meet FabLab mission and cover the gap in the community by 5 years long-term plan. The team take the challenge to elevate and improve the community and FabLab performance by almost 120% by arranging the activities, marketing them and build it up like a chain pieces linked together.

3.1 Merge Current FabLab Activities and Services with the Roadmap

While collecting all data and listing activities we notice that several activates were duplicated and more than one activity working in same objective in different point of view. In addition, some activities were time drainer and in fact not directly affect FabLab performance in reaching the goals. All pervious build up due to unclear goals and multiple decision makers. Having a road map and clear mission and goals help's FabLab ALAHSA to focus.

3.2 Develop Main Paths and Link to Activities and Services

After listing down all FabLab activities and services was delivered to the community, we start group them and merge some till we end up with seven paths as follows in table 2:

Path	What is included?
Ithraa	Ithraa mean enhancing something. This mainly to enhance community knowledge and Arabic content in making and digital fabrication. This part include session and workshop video publishing in YouTube, developing the content of FabCast, which is a broadcast in Arabic about digital fabrication, develop do it yourself (DIY) videos and arranging meeting with experts (FabLab ALAHSA YouTube channel, 2020).
Tamkeen	Tamkeen mean skill up others and make them ready to perform the certain tasks. This path include workshops, sessions, campaigns and competitions.
Project Support	Support individuals and group for any purpose such as personal, university project or business POC project and prototyping.
Fablab Project	Contain project done in FabLab ALAHSA by FabLab team and volunteers.
Community Project	Focused in project planned to be done for the community in public areas with the help of FabLab volunteers and community.
Partnership	This path mainly to have an agreement with special group of experts or organizations and build win-win relationship. This will help FabLab ALAHSA reach to community faster and expedite goals achievement.
Internship	This path focus on having agreements with local universities to open the floor for students to be part of FabLab team and have their training in FabLab. FabLab accept some of the major in Engineering, Management and Media.

Table 4: Seven paths of FabLab ALAHSA

The team later decide to add two more paths, which they are:

Path	What is included?
R&D	Main role of R&D path to enrich research and developing skills and community by having certain number of research papers and projects every year. This paper is one of the outcome of R&D path.
Estidamah	Estidamah mean sustainability. In here, the team focus to have effective spending and looking for partial refunding from projects and activities until reach breakeven value of FabLab operation.

Table 5: Extra paths that included later

Moreover, some of the paths were merged together and end up with only six paths. Shrieking the numbers to six was due to similarities, small scope in some paths and to easy manage by direct each path to one of the permanent team member including the consultant.

Figure 5: FabLab ALAHSa Roadmap

Roadmap and general plan presentation prepared using Prezi (Perzi website, 2020) and shared with Foundation management and AlRashed companies' owner Abdulmonem AlRashed to get final approval (FabLab Al Hassa Road Map, 2020).

3.3 Develop Short Plan for Effectiveness Test

In order to evaluate the team readiness and the effectiveness of the plan with selected paths, FabLab ALAHSa team agreed to develop a short plan in Q4 2020 and squeeze the time to implement pilot of all activities in the roadmap. Plan set it up and implementation started early Oct 2020 with 3 training sessions and workshops, 13 projects. Total attendance and beneficiary of FabLab ALAHSa Activities in Q4 2020 was 1488 comparing to 1562 in whole year of 2019.

Beginning of Q1 2021 FabLab ALAHSa team meet to review and evaluate the achievements and see the performance indication by comparing plan vs actual performance.

- **Ithraa path KPI**

Program	2020 Q4 Planned	Completed
FabCast	3	3
DIY	3	2
FabTalk	1	1
Video publishing	4,3	4

Table 6: Ithraa KPI

- **Tamkeen Path KPI**

Program	2020 Q4 Planned	Completed
Training Workshop	4	4
Campaign	3	2
Volunteer Special Training	1	1

Table 7: Tamkeen KPI

- **Project Path KPI**

Program	2020 Q4 Planned	Completed
Fablab Projects with Volunteers	2	2
FabLab ALAHSa Team Projects	20	19
Project Support Services	2	2

Table 8: Project KPI

- **Partnership Path KPI**

Program	2020 Q4 Planned	Completed
College & University Students	1	1

Table 9: Partnership KPI

- **Estidamah Path KPI**

Program	2020 Q4 Planned	Completed
Volunteer Program	Started	Done

Table 8: Estidamah KPI

3.4 Operation Excellence Procedure for Plan Evaluation and Implementation

Operation excellence (OE) could be summarized in 4 main steps: Plan, Do, Check and Adjust. Following these steps throughout any work in any organization will help a lot to improve the work quality and result. OE step are first; Plan your work, which include identify the gap, plan to overcome and secure resources. Second, we Do the work based on plan along with the checking the quality and if we are in track as third step. Finally, adjust the plan based on the actual implementation, realistic data and challenges team faced during implementation (Proqis, 2018).

Break in Parts for Fast Reach and Easy Measure

In order to reach best result FabLab ALAHSa team divide the roadmap to paths and each part to program and projects. This process help the team to easy implement, fast navigate and follow up. FabLab ALAHSa

team use (ASANA App) as an open source web base task manager (Asana, 2008). Asana very powerful tools for planning, task management, assigning and follow up.

Monitor and Control the Plan

The team in FabLab AIAHSA meet every week to follow up, recognized completed tasks, discussing delayed one, identify challenges and make a corrective actions to meet the goals and implement the plan. In addition, the team meet end of each quarter to discuss achievements and what helps to reach. In addition, failures were identified and what the expected reasons behind then plan to transfer to next quarter or cancel if agreed to replace with other task or mission.

Another meeting held also at the beginning of each quarter to have detailed plan of the upcoming months. During the meeting the team agreed on the tasks, workshops, session and other activities with due date for each one. Materials and resources needed discussed as well with expected cost.

Evaluate the Performance and Create KPI's

Each quarter, one of the team member take the role, prepare a short presentation with help of data collected, and plan to demonstrate FabLab AIAHSA performance. All KPI has showed in the meeting with percentage based on its equation. We have at least one KPI for each path to evaluate the performance based on agreed plan.

3Change Activities and Programs Based on Need

As one of the adjustment process, FabLab AIAHSA team revisit the plan and programs during the weekly meeting and change activities or program if required. The main guidance and role during this process that we have to replace each one with equivalent or better one in same quarter or in the next one. As an example of this is the DIY videos.

DIY videos was marked as time consumer and in the other hand, the views in YOUTUBE are miner compare to the work done by the team. As alternative, we decided to use Reels in Instagram. Reel videos are fast in producing; easy use and follower are more active in Instagram (FabLab Al Hassa Instagram, 2020). In fact, to avoid losing the goal of DIY which is to enhance the Arabic Maker content, we reduce the DIY videos and we did not cancel this program.

Another example of adding part based on need and after evaluation is FAB App. FAB App is a web base application build on glide app, which is web help you to build application for different proposes using Google excel sheets Glideapps (2020). FAB App containing multi tabs showing FabLab information, activities, services and channels FabApp (2020). Front tab showing all new activities in FabLab AIAHSA from newest to old, followed by information tab about the Lab. Information tab containing the contact information, location, broadcast episode about FabLabs and FabLab content from equipment and tools. Third tab designated for FabLab AIAHSA services, which are reservation of workspace or machine, reservation of Fab studio, request consulting and register as volunteer. Last tab is for FabLab AIAHSA production series of sessions, broadcasts, workshops, meeting, DIYs and pervious competitions. Fab App improve the communication between FabLab AIAHSA and users by easiness the reservation process, giving general information about FabLabs and enhance process of requesting FabLab services.

Figure 6: Fablab team weekly meeting for monitor and control

Figure 7: Fablab Team during evaluation performance session

4 Enhance FabLab Equipments

4.1 How to Select FabLab Equipment Based on FabLab Goals and Paths

One of the main item to improve and having effective FabLab is to select the right equipment with the right quantities. Having roadmap and long term-plan along with record demand of the lab of projects gave us wider angle to see upcoming need expectation of growth community. At the beginning of the FabLab, we were having 3 main 3D printer only. We notice that the demand is high and as it know that 3D printers consume lot of time, we ordered more 3D printers and we focus to order open source controllers.

Figure 8: 3D printing zone

In the other side, some equipment have very low usage record such as milling machine. This low utilization are due two main reasons: 1. difficulty of the programs used with machines especially they are not open source. 2. Most of FabLab ALAHSA users are students and makers want to build prototypes and those focus in three main zones which is electronics, 3D printing and laser cutting. The incorrect selection of FabLab equipments are because the team work in foundation of FabLab ALAHSA are not from the same area and they build it based on their experience in their country.

As a result, long term-plan to be build based on the community need and gaps need to be filled is a big milestone during FabLab structure.

Figure 9: Milling machine and laser cutting zone

5 Escalate Community Involvement to Reach Goals Faster

Engaging the community members in the programs and activities that FabLab ALAHSA holds have shown a tremendous accelerative effect on how fast the FabLab achieves goals.

These engagements can be categorized into attracting makers to participate in the FabLab, establishing connections with maker's groups and volunteer's participation.

5.1 Attracting Makers through Contests and Programs

Makers exist in all communities. However, they need a place that has an attractive environment to gather them in order to work on turning their ideas into projects. FabLab is one of the greatest places that offers a creative environment in which makers can work on their projects.

FabLab AIAHSA has worked on programs and activities that targeted the makers to create a maker community in AIAHSA, and these programs can be divided into the following:

- **Workshops**

Since the launch of FabLab AIAHSA in 2018, it has offered workshops in the following fields: 3D printing and 3D designing, laser cutting and CNC machines and 2D designing, electronics and Arduino. Moreover, FabLab AIAHSA has started offering workshops for kids. A passionate team has worked on training kids on electronics, 3D printing, art and music. These workshops raised the awareness of digital fabrication in the local community and hence experts started to contact us to participate with us in delivering workshops to the community.

Figure 10: FabLab AIAHSA electronics workshop

Figure 11: 3D workshop at FabLab ALAHSa

- **Meetups**

The meetups that FabLab ALAHSa has worked on are gathered under one project which is called FabTalk.

These FabTalks were supposed to be on-site. However, because of the COVID-19 pandemic, the team has decided to deliver these sessions online. The experts and the topics that we have hosted so far are as follows:

Topic: Simplifying Sciences

Guest: Ali AlBahrani, an engineer who has successful YouTube channel focusing on simplifying sciences.

3D Printing Technologies

Guest: Faisal AlAmer, an engineer who owns a 3D printing company.

Scientific Research

Guest: Hussain AlSalamin, an engineer and an expert researcher in King Faisal University in ALAHSa, Saudi Arabia.

Topic: Bring Your Ideas to the Market

Guests: Abdullah Bahabri, owns a company specialized in customized perfumes.

Mohammed Albayti and Mohanad Alqurashi, own a start-up specialized in water consumption control.

During all the four mentioned topics, the attendees on both Zoom and YouTube exceeded 100 attendees per session. Not only that, but the attendees were also very diverse, people from different parts of Saudi Arabia and from different countries. Attendees were allowed to interact with guests by asking questions related to the topic of the session. These talks participated in attracting more makers to our FabLab by attending our programs virtually and physically.

Figure 12: Engineer Ahmed Al Hajji in 1st FabTalk meetup

Figure 13: Engineer Mahmoud Al Mohammed with Artist Atheer and maker Majed in one of FabLab meetup for makers

- **Bootcamps**

Bootcamps or campaigns help trainees to learn faster than normal workshops; we have worked on bootcamps that targeted high school students, university students and even those who are interested even if they are seniors. Because we believe that knowledge is for everyone.

One of the biggest bootcamps that we have worked on was entitled by Enability, which was held at FabLab AIAHSA in cooperation with the Ministry of Education. The scope of this bootcamp was to find solutions to the challenges that people with special needs are facing.

The bootcamp gathered 30 talented students, 15 of them were from different cities from Saudi Arabia and the other 15 were from Taiwan. Students were divided into groups and then were introduced and trained on 3 sections of FabLab AIAHSA which are 3D printing, laser cutting machines and electronics and Arduino.

After the training phase ended, the trainees worked with their groups on projects that tackles selected challenges people with special needs face.

5.2 Establishing Connections with Groups

AIAHSA is a city of handcrafts since the old days, and craftsmen have concerns about technologies and machines replacing them and taking their jobs away. That is why; we are working at FabLab AIAHSA to raise the awareness of how craftsmen can integrate with FabLabs to work together on the same handcrafts.

We have started reaching out to well-known craftsmen such as Hasanin Al Ramel, who is specialized on woodcrafts and specially on making masterpieces about Arabic alphabets. He believes that craftsmen can take advantage of advanced machines and technology to enhance the quality of their work.

Moreover, we have collaborated with groups specialized in electronics and robotics such as Robo Hajir, a well-known group in AIAHSA which has been there for years. We worked on projects together and members of this team worked along with FabLab AIAHSA team on bootcamps and workshops which helped in speeding the process of reaching the community and achieving goals.

5.3 Volunteers Programs

In support of the community partnership we seek, we started a volunteers' technical program which aims at qualifying interested community members in digital fabrication training; this program intends to prepare volunteers to be technical specialists in FabLab AIAHSA; they can assist our team during the workshops and services FabLab AIAHSA team provides.

- **During the program, volunteers were trained as follows:**

- **First week:**

Training all volunteers on the basics of all machines available in the lab.

- **The second week:**

The volunteers were divided into groups according to their interests, and each group was intensively trained to use the machines they chose to be specialized in.

After the success of the volunteer's technical preparation program, volunteers started to participate with FabLab AIAHSA team in workshops and projects as if they were employees in the lab. We have also opened the door to volunteer in media; people who are expert in photography, videography and designing became part of FabLab AIAHSA volunteers' team.

Figure 14: Volunteers program during CNC & milling machine workshop

6 Examples and statistics

In this part of the paper, KPIs for each path will be illustrated in the tables below for the 1st and 2nd quarter of 2021.

Ithraa Path KPIs:

Program	Q1 Planned	Q2 Planned
FabCast	1	1
DIY	4	1
Short Educational Videos		3
FabTalk	1	1
Video publishing	3	4
What is FabLab?		Film

Table 9: Ithraa path KPIs for 1st and 2nd quarter of 2021

Tamkeen Path KPIs:

Program	Q1 Planned	Q2 Planned
Training	7	9
Campaign	1	1
Group Cooperation	1	-
Start-up support	prepare	start
Competition	1	1
Kids Lab Workshops	18	18
Kids Lab Programs	3	3

Table 10: Tamkeen path KPIs for 1st and 2nd quarter of 2021

Project Path KPIs:

Program	Q1 Planned	Q2 Planned
Fablab Projects with Volunteers	1	
Fablab ALAHSA Team Projects	-	1
Project Support Services	50	50
Community Projects	-	start

Table 11: Project path KPIs for 1st and 2nd quarter of 2021

Partnership Path KPIs:

Program	Q1 Planned	Q2 Planned
Internship	1	2-3
partnership	-	1

Table 12: Partnership path KPIs for 1st and 2nd quarter of 2021

R&D Path KPIs:

Program	Q1 Planned	Q2 Planned
Research Paper	prepare	start
R&D Project	prepare	start

Table 13: R&D path KPIs for 1st and 2nd quarter of 2021

Estidamah Path KPIs:

Program	Q1 Planned	Q2 Planned
Local Store		Prepare location and stuff
Website & Membership	System prepare	System prepare

Table 14: Estidamah path KPIs for 1st and 2nd quarter of 2021

Statistics

This is part will show the effect of long-term plan in the numbers of beneficiary at FabLab AIAHSA. The numbers are clearly illustrated in the table below that include online programs beneficiaries which started in Q3 2020:

Types of Beneficiaries	Number of Beneficiaries		
	2019	2020	until July 2021
Workshops & Programs Beneficiaries	604	8278	4536
Volunteers	25	46	65
Visitors	918	301	145
Projects Support Services Beneficiaries	41	150	391
Total	1588	8775	5137

Table 15: Total number and types of beneficiaries at FabLab AIAHSA

Figure 15: Total number and types of beneficiaries at FabLab AIAHSA

7 Conclusion

Sustainability for FabLab is not direct issue can be solve in one way or even several specific ways. FabLab sustainability depend on funding, machine developments, operation plan and community need. In this paper, we focus on plan sector and especially on long-term plan, which can help us to visualize the future and having always clear vision of the next step.

FabLab ALAHSA case study show the powerful of long-term plan along with organized implementation using operation excellence process. In addition, we have to know the community needs, gaps, expectation and identify local resources and capabilities before start building the long-term plan. Moreover, one of the main item of success of FabLab ALAHSA is the continues follow up and frequent meeting to make sure the plan is followed and adjust the implementation of programmes, workshops and projects based on statistics and KPIs you follow up in the frequent meetings.

Multi factors effect in FabLab performance and ensure sustainability. Although we focus on good planning and having vision in this paper, but they are more factors support the case such as using open source powerful software is for task management and follow up, improve communication with community. We will leave other parts for future papers to discuss with the FabLab network community such as volunteering programs, role of women in FabLab ALAHSA; open source tools to improve performance, effect of FabLab in work generation, role of FabLab in improve artwork and roles of FabLab to lead the 4.0 industrial revolution.

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